

MORPHOLOGICAL SIGNS THAT DEVELOP IN THE STOMACH OF WHITE-BREED RATS IN EXPERIMENTAL PULMONARY FIBROSIS

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Relevance: a deterioration in environmental conditions among the countries of the world, an increase in various risk factors negatively affect the human body. As a result of the development of pathological processes, a number of morphometric and morphological changes occurred in the anatomical structure and mucous membranes of the stomach. The medical and social significance of digestive diseases (OHQCS) is determined by their prevalence, as well as the annual increase in the percentage of morbidity and mortality.

keywords : similarity, parameters, changes, stomach, rats

Pulmonary fibrosis is a chronic lung disease characterized by progressive scarring of the tissues covering the organ. When the wall of the pulmonary alveoli (sac-like structures where smaller caliber bronchial branches end) thickens and its surface is covered with a progressive scar, their gas exchange capacity decreases. As a result, the alveoli cannot supply enough oxygen to the blood and cellular respiration is disrupted. On the other hand, carbon dioxide, which must pass through the blood to the alveoli, cannot be exchanged for oxygen. As a result, the body does not receive enough oxygen-saturated blood (that is, purified from carbon dioxide and saturated with oxygen). Over time, scar tissue overlies the capillaries of the pulmonary alveoli, making gas exchange even more difficult. This process, in turn, causes dangerous consequences for the circulatory system and the heart.

Most often, this disease develops in people over 40 years of age, mainly in men. It then reduces the formation of fibrosis (scarred) tissue. In viral pneumonia, in COVID-19, the main pathological changes occur precisely in this carapace (interstitial) that surrounds each part in particular. The walls of the vessels passing through it thin out, do not hold the liquid part of the blood well. It begins to protrude beyond the veins. Interstitial tissue swells, but part of the air remains in the alveoli themselves, so that a characteristic "dullness" appears on the X-ray

The purpose of the study: experimental pulmonary fibrosis called Study of morphological changes that occur in the stomach of white-breed rats.

Research methods and techniques: 150 of both sexes grown under standard vivarium conditions for experimental scientific research, age 3-12 months, Weight 200 gr. - 500 gr. rats without a white breed were selected. Laboratory animals were kept in the vivarium of the Bukhara State Medical Institute. Rats were cared for in special rooms according to the requirements for rooms where experimental animals were kept (room temperature 20-24°C, humidity 60%, lighting 12 hours).

The animals were given enough water and fed with a balanced diet. When preparing and conducting experimental research, it was taken into account that proper care and feeding of laboratory animals is of great importance. Violation of the regime and diet, non-compliance with hygienic measures during feeding leads to a weakening of the animal's body. Increases their susceptibility to various infectious and somatic diseases. The appearance of these diseases during the experiment can lead to a violation of the results of the study and, as a result, to incorrect conclusions.

To determine whether or not there are other diseases and their age, they were subject to a mandatory vet examination. In order to prevent the entry of infectious diseases into the vivarium, the adopted animals were quarantined for 21 days. Laboratory animals were kept in special cages installed on the shelves. The total number of white broodless rats in the cage, the date of the start of the experiment and the last name of the researcher responsible for conducting it are indicated in the experimental animal cage.

Results and discussions: in the macroscopic examination of the stomach in the expressive pulmonary fibrosis, The Shape of the abdomen, located on the hook, the color of the whitish liver, macroscopically pronounced pathological signs were identified

On microscopic examination, the mucous (bicarbonate layer thickness) located on the surface of the gastric mucosa is reduced. The number of cells located deep on the surface and neck of the gastric mucosa has not changed significantly, but their size is slightly smaller than that of the control group, dystrophic signs are visible in the cells of the mucous membrane, swelling when the mucous membrane and musculature are seen, signs of fullness are detected in the veins located in the

White rats in the control group and white non-breeding rats with experimental pulmonary fibrosis were compared with each other in morphological and morphometric indicators of stomachs. When examined macroscopically, serous inflammation is prominent over the gastric mucosa.

Conclusion:

In a microscopic examination of the stomach of all rats in a group called experimental pulmonary fibrosis, hyperfunctions of the mucous membrane naysayers were detected. In this one-layer prismatic epithelium hypersecretory appearance, serous inflammatory infiltrate, mucous membrane: hypertrophy of sparse fibrous connective tissue, fullness of blood vessels, lymphocyte infiltrate, hyperplasia of glands located on a private plate: HyperChrome staining of the core, shrinkage of cytoplasm, hypertrophy of muscle fibers on the muscular floor, swelling in the inter-muscular space.

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